

Investigation of Mid-term Migration Scenarios to Multi-Band Solutions in Metropolitan Networks

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ABSTRACT

The evolution toward beyond-5G/6G services and applications requiring very high bandwidths will put ever-growing pressure on deployed optical networks to provide the spectral resources needed to accommodate such traffic loads. This is particularly true for the metro/regional segments, where expected traffic CAGR exceeding 40%, primarily driven by CDN traffic confined to the network segments closer to the end users, will push the fiber capacity to its fundamental limits on a number of “hot” links in the short to medium term, irrespective of the use of spectrally efficient modulation formats, especially suited for short-haul transmission. It is therefore critical to evaluate migration scenarios to expand spectral resources beyond the extended C-band (4.8 THz) mainly in use today. In this paper, we conduct multi-homed edge-to-core routing, modulation-level and spectrum-assignment simulations over Telefónica reference metropolitan networks, considering bandwidth-variable coherent transmission with per-channel capacity of 100-400 Gbps in 50 GHz and link-by-link C+L-band migration, while ensuring optimal GSNR performance. Results show that the rollout of L-band equipment over a reduced number of links can efficiently extend the lifespan of current networks, guaranteeing congestion-free operation with minimal intervention, and can be a suitable transitional capacity-stretching solution prior to undertaking more disruptive multi-fiber deployments.

Keywords: multi-band, spectrum assignment, network migration, metropolitan networks.

1. INTRODUCTION

To cater to the capacity demands of future services anticipated to emerge after 2030, which would have an impact on the Radio Access Networks (RAN), particularly in the case of split option 7.1 or 8, but also in other network segments up to the core (more specifically in densely populated metropolitan regions), it is imperative to increase the available bandwidth. This can be achieved by two methods: augmenting the usable fiber spectrum via multi-band solutions and deploying Space-Division Multiplexing (SDM) fibers. Commercial solutions for the C+L-bands are in their initial stages of availability, and there is ongoing research into alternative optical spectrum bands extending over the L, S, E, and O bands, which are being investigated as a viable and economical solution to further increase the spectral resources [1]. Nonetheless, implementing broader spectral transmission systems leads to a decline in channel performance predominantly caused by Stimulated Raman Scattering (SRS). One possible solution to alleviate this transmission performance degradation is utilizing SDM, which may be a desirable option in a fiber-rich environment. It is therefore evident that a plan for migration must be established to facilitate this transition. Several studies have been conducted on this subject. In [2], three C- to C+L-band link-level methods were evaluated: multi-fiber, C+L-band from day one, and a pay-as-you-grow (PAYG) approach. Among them, PAYG stands out as an efficient and cost-effective method, involving the implementation of modular multi-band terminal and line system equipment. Migration to multi-fiber and C+L-band from day one was explored in [3] and [4], whereas [5] investigated migration to C+L-band in fixed-grid and flexi-grid scenarios, and [6] and [7] examined mid-term migration from C- to C+L+S-band and multi-fiber, respectively, but did not account for SRS. Finally, [8] presented migration to C+SupC+L-band as well as to C+L+S using translucent and transparent strategies, SupC standing for “super C-band” and adding 1.2 THz to the 4.8 THz of the extended C-band. All these works considered incremental traffic (except in [5]) over backbone networks without accounting for survivability. In contrast, this paper investigates three mid-term migration scenarios based on multiband/multi-fiber solutions in a large metropolitan optical network, applying multi-period planning, survivability and PAYG.

2. SYSTEM MODEL AND ASSUMPTIONS

The reference network topology considered in this paper (see Fig. 1.a) is a Telefónica metro-urban network composed of 93 optical nodes and 126 links. At the IP layer, the network is structured into five hierarchical levels [9], but this study concentrates on the four highest levels (HL1-HL4): the interconnection nodes (HL1), serving as interfaces to other telecom providers and the internet, the transit nodes (HL2), linking the HL3 aggregation nodes to the HL1 nodes and also hosting major datacenters, and the HL4 nodes, which aggregate traffic from the access points. This hierarchical distribution separates out the physical topology into three

Figure 1. (a) Metro-urban network topology, (b) An illustrative example of aggregation strategy for HLx nodes and lower-level co-located HLx nodes. HL4 domain: green nodes and blue links, HL3 domain: black nodes and red links, HL2 domain: pink (HL2s) and blue (HL1s) nodes and black links.

independent network segments extending from the access rings/partial meshes (connecting HL4s together and with pairs of HL3 nodes, depicted by the light blue links in Fig. 1.a) to the metro/core meshed network (consisting of two segments: the connections between HL3s and from HL3s to HL2s –red links–, and the connections between HL2s and from HL2s to HL1s –dark blue links–). In the following, we will refer to these segments as the HL4, HL3 and HL2 domain, respectively. IP traffic is transmitted from each node to two different nodes belonging to an immediately higher hierarchical level (multi-homing). In order not to impose further restrictions on the routing, modulation format, and spectrum assignment (RMSA), we assume that all optical nodes are equipped with colorless, directionless, and contentionless (CDC) re-configurable optical add-drop multiplexers (ROADM) and sufficient bandwidth-variable transponders (BVTs) or fixed capacity transponders that operate under a license-based client port activation scheme. The chosen throughput, symbol rate, roll-off factor, channel spacing, and pre-FEC BER overhead are 100-400 Gbps, 40 GBaud, 0.1, 50 GHz, and 25%, respectively.

3. PROPOSED ALGORITHMS FOR METRO NETWORK MULTI-PERIOD PLANNING

We propose a multi-period planning strategy consisting of seven steps: **1**-Network partitioning: partition the network into three domains (HL4, HL3, and HL2 domains); **2**-Destination selection: identify all candidate destinations from the HLx nodes in the HLx domain, e.g. in the HL4 domain, candidate HL3 nodes are identified for all HL4s; **3**-Path list creation: pre-calculate all paths between the HLx nodes in the HLx domain and the selected candidate destinations according to minimum hop number or shortest distance; **4**- Selection of primary and secondary pairs (PSPs) of paths: find all link- and node-disjoint pairs (primary and secondary paths from each HLx node to two destination nodes) in the path list in **step 3**; **5**-Spectrum, band, and fiber-pair assignment: calculate the number of required transponders according to the requested bit-rate (R) from $\lceil (R - R_{res}) / R_{base} \rceil$, where R_{res} , R_{base} are the residual (i.e. already in use) and base (maximum) capacity of the transponder, and perform the spectrum, band, and fiber-pair assignment based on the first-fit approach; **6**-Path selection: select the optimum PSP based on the minimum cost of the candidate PSPs, i.e., $\text{Min } C_p = \sum_{l=1}^{M_p} N_{l,p} L_{l,p}$, where C_p , M_p , $N_{l,p}$ and $L_{l,p}$ are the cost function for PSP p , the total number of links that are part of the primary and secondary routes in PSP p , the number of fiber pairs in link l of PSP p , and the length of link l in PSP p ; **7**-Aggregation: aggregate the traffic from each HLx node at the two destinations to which it is paired. Thus, half of the traffic is homed to each of the destinations.

In contrast to [10], which proposed a partially disjoint path for both nodes and links, we introduce a k-pair link-and-node-disjoint (LAND) strategy for PSPs. To implement this, we first partition the metro network into three domains in step 1. This ensures that traffic from each lower HL node does not traverse the same links as the aggregated traffic from higher HL nodes. To generate the lists of LAND PSPs, we pre-calculate all the paths between the lower HL nodes and the higher HL nodes in that domain. In this step, we store the list of links, length, and number of hops for each path as path attributes. Next, for each primary path, we select a secondary path whose destination nodes and links are distinct from the primary path. Finally, the LAND PSPs are sorted in ascending order based on their number of hops/distances.

To ensure survivability, in a multi-homing approach, only 50% of the aggregated IP traffic at a node is provisioned to each of the transponders connected to the two upper HL nodes, whereas the provisioned capacity of the optical channels (OC) from both transponders needs to be 100% of the aggregated IP traffic to guarantee that all traffic can reach the next hierarchical level in the event of a link or node failure. However, the calculation of OC capacities in the HL2 domain becomes more complicated in the case of HL1 nodes co-located with nodes from other domains in the same site, as the reference topology under consideration only contains two HL1 nodes,

Table 1. Statistics related to the reference metropolitan topology in Fig. 1.a for $k \leq 3$.

Parameter	HL4s Domain	HL3s Domain	HL2s Domain
Mean nodal degrees	2.27	2.81	5.5
Mean link distances [km]	9.37	13.13	40.17
Mean established lightpaths [km]	51.32	60.57	116.61
Number of links	$24 \times 3 = 72$	47	7

as shown in Fig. 1.a. In all other cases, OC capacities guaranteeing node-failure robustness can be calculated as explained in the first sentence of this paragraph provided that co-located HL3 nodes are not hubbed to co-located HL2 nodes. Fig.1.b can be used to explain the formula for the calculation of the OC capacity in the HL2 domain, which is given by $R/(N_p - N_{p-c})$, where R is the aggregated traffic at the HL2 node, N_p is the number of primary (P) and secondary (S) paths hubbed to the HL1 node under study, and N_{p-c} is the number of paths (P or S) hubbed to the HL1 site under study originating from HL2 or HL3 nodes co-located with the other HL1 node. In this study we use a license-based transponder capacity increase scheme, whereby the number of 100G licenses is calculated from $\lceil (R - R_{res})/100 \rceil$, where R is the requested bit rate and R_{res} is the residual vacancy from previous years. Three migration strategies are proposed based on PAYG: (1) C+NFP, (2) C+SupC+NFP, and (3) C+SupC+L+NFP, where NFP stands for “New Fiber Pair”. 4.8 THz C-band is used in C+NFP, where new C-band systems are deployed when the requested throughput exceeds the available resources in the existing. For C+SupC+NFP, we consider the same approach but the available spectrum in the NFPs is 6 THz. Moreover, SupC transponders are deployed when the C-band cannot accommodate more traffic in a given link, but in this case, due to the continuity constraint, all links that are part of the end-to-end path need to be migrated to SupC. Once the SupC resources are exhausted, a NFP is used. The same strategy is considered for C+SupC+L+NFP, with a total bandwidth of 12.5 THz per fiber pair and a 500-GHz guard band between the C- and the L-band. Modular L-band ROADMs and in-line amplifiers are assumed to be deployed based on PAYG when required.

4. SIMULATIONS AND RESULTS

The performance of the three migration strategies proposed above is evaluated with the topology shown in Fig. 1.a, composed of 54 HL4s, 33 HL3s (4 of which have co-located HL4s), 4 HL2s (with co-located HL3, and one co-located HL4), and 2 HL1s (with co-located HL2s, and one co-located HL4). The aggregated traffic at the HL4 nodes is uniformly generated in the range of 20-200 Gbps with average 100 Gbps, with a 40% compound annual growth rate (CAGR), according to [9]. We select PM-64QAM 400G transponders (based on a 100G licensing scheme) with 50GHz channel spacing and pre-FEC BER 10^{-3} , and consider k-shortest path ≤ 3 to guarantee the GSNR requirement. The number of 50-GHz channels is 96, 120, and 240 for strategies 1-3, respectively. Some statistics about the reference network are reported in Table 1. The longest established lightpath is 116.61 km, while the maximum reach for PM-64QAM is about 150 km for C+L-band transmission [11].

Fig. 2.a-c show that the links in the HL4 domain do not require SupC, L-band or NFP for the next ten years, unlike in HL3/ HL2 domains. As shown in Fig. 2.a, NFP is required from Y7(8) in some links of the HL3 (HL2) domain. The better behavior of the HL2 domain is due to the higher nodal degree and the number of LAND PSP for HL2s.

Fig. 3.a-c display the cumulative NFP per year. The results reveal that the number of NFP in the HL2 domain is lower than in the HL3 domain, but the cumulative length of NFP used in the HL2 domain is higher. The C+SupC+L-band strategy reduces NFP use, as in Y10 only three NFP with a cumulative length of ~14 km are needed (See Fig. 2.c and Fig. 3.c). In Fig. 4.a-c, we plot the number of transponders and 100G licenses. In the HL4 domain, the cumulative number of 400G transponders remains constant for the first three years (see Fig. 4.a), but afterward we observe an annual increase of 28% in the number of 400G transponders, slightly less pronounced than the increase observed for the HL3 and HL2 domains (~38%). The total number of 400G

Figure 2. Fiber usage per link year over year for (a) C+NFP, (b) C+SupC+NFP, and (c) C+SupC+L+NFP. NFP: New Fiber Pair, C, SupC, and L: C-Band, Super-C-Band, and L-Band, respectively.

Figure 3. Cumulative fiber-pair usage in km (left-hand side axis) and number of fiber pairs (right-hand side axis) over ten years. See Fig.2 caption for acronyms.

Figure 4. Cumulative number of BVT (left-hand side axis) and 100G-license usage (right-hand side axis) over ten years for all scenarios. See Fig.2 caption for acronyms.

transponders and 100G licenses is 3888 and 5092, respectively, for all strategies. However, Fig.4.b shows that the number of SupC-band 400G transponders and 100G licenses increase from 0.8% to 7% and from 0.2% to 0.3%, respectively, of the corresponding amount in years 7-10, and in Fig.4.c the L-band transponder presence in the network increases from 3% to 13%.

5. CONCLUSIONS

The study reveals that the deployment of C+L-band solutions on a limited number of links can considerably increase the longevity of current networks, leading to a significant reduction in the requirement for new fiber deployments. However, the adoption of new technology typically entails a cost premium of approximately 20% compared to the existing technology [3]. Therefore, it is essential to perform a techno-economic study to evaluate the cost-effectiveness of L-band equipment under different scenarios. Nonetheless, this approach can function as an interim measure to meet the escalating network capacity demands in the medium term.

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